

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF SELF MICROEMULSIFYING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM OF LURASIDONE HCl

Komal Rahevar^{*}, Dr. Mukesh R. Patel, Dr. Kanu R. Patel

Gujarat Technological University, Gujarat.

Shri B. M. Shah College of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, College Campus, Dhansura Road, Modasa- 383 315. (Arvalli)

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 05/04/2016

Available online

01/01/2018

Keywords

SMEDDS,
Lurasidone Hcl,
Bioavailability,
In-Vitro Release Study.

ABSTRACT

Objective: Lurasidone HCl is poorly water soluble drug. It should be come in to the BCS Class II drug. Hence oral Bioavailability of Lurasidone HCl is less (9-19%). To develop novel dosage foam of the self-Microemulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS) for the Lurasidone HCl for enhancing its solubility hence the oral bioavailability. Methods: Solubility study was performed in different excipient and selected excipient on basis of solubility of Lurasidone HCl. Self microemulsion region was decided by preparing construction phase diagram. Drug excipient interaction study using FTIR. SMEDDS formulation was prepared in Capryol 90 (oil), Acrysol K-140(surfactant), and Transcutol P (co-surfactant) by simple mixing at 25°C. Parameters evaluated included: macroscopic evaluation, visual assessment, self-emulsification, transmittance test, particle size distribution, zeta potential and polydispersity index and *In vitro* dissolution. *In-Vitro* dissolution was carried in USP apparatus II using pH 1.2 HCl buffer at 37±0.5°C with 75 rpm rotating speed, drug release measured by spectroscopic method. Results: From the solubility study, better solubility was seen in Capryol 90(oil), Acrysol K 140(surfactant) and Transcutol P (co-surfactant). Optimized formulation F3 of SMEDDS was observed with smaller droplet size 57.35nm, PDI 0.288 and zeta potential -13.6mV⁵. Formulation was clear after dilution with water. SMEDDS formulations showed complete release in 60 minutes as compared with pure drug Lurasidone HCl (20mg).which showed a limited dissolution rate. Conclusion: SMEDDS Lurasidone HCl oral formulations were prepared that provides excellent drug solubilization and improved *In-Vitro* release of Lurasidone HCl.

Gujarat, India.

Corresponding author

Komal H. Rahevar

Shri B. M. Shah College of Pharmaceutical Education and Research,

College Campus, Dhansura Road, Modasa- 383 315.

(Arvalli) Gujarat, India.

komalrahevar.kr@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Komal H. Rahevar** et al. Design and Development of Self Microemulsifying Drug Delivery System of Lurasidone Hcl. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2017:7(12).

Copy right © 2017 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION

Oral route is still remain most favorite route of drug administration in many diseases and till today it is the first way of investigation in the development of new dosage form. Low aqueous solubility is a major problem faced during formulation development of new drug molecules. This may lead to high inter and intra subject variability and require of dose proportionality. To solve this problem, we need to enhancement of bioavailability of weakly water soluble drug so it is one of the big challenges for drug formulation. Various technological strategies are reported in the literature like micronization, solid dispersion or cyclodextrines complex formation for increase the solubility and bioavailability of drug. Self microemulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS) is isotropic mixtures of oils, surfactant and co-surfactant and drugs which emulsify spontaneously to produce fine oil-in-water emulsion when introduced into aqueous phase under gentle agitation. It has gain more attention due to enhanced oral bioavailability, enabling reduction in dose of drug, more steady temporal profile of drug absorption, selective targeting of drug toward specific absorption window in gastrointestinal tract, and protection of drug from the hostile environment in gut. Lurasidone HCl is atypical antipsychotic drug approved by the U.S Food and Drug Administration for treatment of schizophrenia and depressive episodes associated bipolar depression. It act by antagonizing serotonin (5HT_{2A}) and dopamine (D₂) receptor and is thought to improve the negative symptoms of psychoses and reduce extra pyramidal side effects which are associated with typical antipsychotics.

Lurasidone HCl is BCS class II Drug having high protein binding (98%). The drug has poor oral bioavailability (9-19%) due to its low aqueous solubility (0.224mg/ml) with delayed onset of action. Hence, it is necessary to improve the aqueous solubility and dissolution rate of Lurasidone HCl to obtain faster onset action and improve oral bioavailability in emergency clinical situation like sudden episodes of psychic attack for schizophrenic patients. [1,2,3].

MATERIALS

Lurasidone HCl was obtained as a gift sample from (Apotax Pharma, Bangalore.), Capryol 90 and Transcutol P were obtained as a gift samples from (Gattefosse, France), Acrysol K 140 was obtained as a gift sample from (Corel chem. , Ahmadabad , India).

METHODS

PREFORMULATION STUDY FOR LURASIDONE HCl

Organoleptic properties:

Colour:

White to off white powder

Odour:

Odourless

Taste:

Metallic bitter

Solubility:

Soluble in water (0.185mg/ml), soluble in methanol (15.6mg/ml)

Melting point

The melting point of Lurasidone HCl was found out by capillary method using Thiele's tube melting point apparatus and was compared with the literature survey. Melting point of Lurasidone HCl was found to be 253⁰C (Average of 3 samples), (255,253,250) melting point range of drug was 250-255⁰C thus it indicating the purity of drug sample.

Identification of Lurasidone HCl:

The FTIR of pure drug was recorded by the drug lurasidone HCl mixed thoroughly with potassium bromide, an infrared transparent matrix, at 1:10 (Drug: KBr) ratio. The KBr discs were prepared by compressing the powders, scan were obtained at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, from 4,000-400 cm⁻¹.

Solubility studies

(screening of Oils, Surfactants, and Co-surfactant)

Two ml of selected oil, surfactant and co-surfactant were added to each cap vial containing an excess of Lurasidone HCl. After sealing, mixing of the systems was performed using a vortex mixer. Formed mixture was shaken with a shaker at 25°C for 24 hours under room temperature to attain equilibrium; each vial was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 minutes. Excess insoluble Lurasidone HCl was discarded by filtration using 0.45µm filter disk. The Supernant was taken and diluted with 0.1 N HCl and UV absorbance was measured at 315 nm. Concentration of dissolved drug was determined using standard equation.[4].

Construction of Phase Diagrams

Pseudo ternary phase diagrams were constructed to obtain the appropriate components and their concentration ranges that can result in large existence area of microemulsion. Surfactant (Acrysol K 140) and co-surfactant (Transcutol P) were mixed (SMix) in different volume ratios (1:1, 2:1, 1:2). For each phase diagram, oil (Capryol 90) and specific surfactant/co-surfactant ratio were mixed thoroughly in different volume ratios from 1:9 to 9:1 in different glass vials. Pseudo ternary phase diagrams were developed using the aqueous titration method. Slow titration with the aqueous phase was performed for each combination of oil and SMix separately. The amount of aqueous phase added was varied to produce a water concentration in the range of 5% to 95% of total volume at around 5% time intervals. The scale up of proportions is easy, as the system is thermodynamically suitable. After each 5% addition of the aqueous phase to the oil: SMix mixture, visual observation was made and recorded. In similar manner, calculations for the other ratios oil and SMix were also done. For each SMix ratio, a separate phase diagram was constructed, and for each phase diagram visual observations were recorded. The pseudo ternary phase diagram was constructed using SIGMA plot software based on the visual observations noted.[4].

Physicochemical compatibility of drug to polymer

FTIR Studies

An FTIR-8400S spectrophotometer (shimadzu, Japan) equipped with attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory was used to obtain the infrared spectra of drug in the isotropic mixture of excipient. For the preparation of solid SMEDDS, the selected liquid SMEDDS (Lurasidone HCl content 20mg) formulation was mixed with solid carrier, Aerosil 200. Briefly, the SMEDDS was added drop wise over the solid adsorbent contained in a porcelain dish. This damp mass passed through sieve no.120 dried at ambient temperature and stored until further use. For each the spectrum, 8 scans were obtained at resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ from a frequency range of 4000-400cm⁻¹.

FOEMULATION OF SMEDDS

The formulation was prepared by initially dissolving required quantity of Lurasidone HCl in oil. Then surfactant and co-surfactant mixer were added and final mixture was mixed by vortexing until a clear solution was obtained. The formulation was equilibrated at ambient temperature for at least 24 hrs, and examined for signs of turbidity or phase separation.

Table 1: SMEDDS formulation of Lurasidone HCl.

Ingredient	Batch (ml)					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Capryol 90	0.2	0.25	0.15	0.2	0.1	0.15
Acrysol k 140	0.4	0.375	0.570	0.540	0.300	0.280
Transcutol P	0.4	0.375	0.280	0.260	0.600	0.570
*Amount of 20mg drug in 1 ml SMEDDS formulation						

EVALUATION OF SMEDDS FORMULATION

Determination of self emulsification time

The formulations were prepared 1 ml of each formulation to standard dissolution apparatus (USP type II) containing 0.1 N HCl p-at 37±0.5C gentle agitation was by paddle rotating at 50 rpm. Emulsification time was assessed visually and categorized into grades. [5]

% Transmission test

Stability of microemulsion formulation with respect to dilution was checked by measuring transmittance through U.V spectrophotometer. Transmittance of samples was measured at 650nm and for each sample three replicate assays were performed.[5]

Visual assessment

The quantity of SMEDDS was assessed by visual inspection and it was graded in various grades. 1ml of each formulation was diluted with purified water (500ml) and gently stirred with magnetic stirrer at 37°C.[6]

Table 2: visual assessments.

Grade	Dispersibility and appearance	Time of self micro-emulsification
I	Rapid forming Microemulsion which is clear or slightly bluish in appearance	< 1 min
II	Rapid forming, slightly less clear emulsion which has a bluish white appearance	< 2 min
III	Bright white emulsion	< 3 min
IV	Dull, grayish white emulsion with a slightly oily appearance that is slow to emulsify	> 3 min
V	Exhibit poor or minimal emulsification with large oil droplets present on the surface	> 3 min

Drug content

Lurasidone HCl from SMEDDS formulation was added in volumetric flask containing 0.1 N HCl. The solutions were filtered, using wattman filter paper. The sample was analyzed for the Lurasidone HCl content spectrophotometrically at 315 nm using standard curve.[6]

Robustness to dilution

Robustness to dilution was studied by diluting it 1000 times with water and 0.1N HCl. The diluted microemulsion was stored for 12hr and observed for any signs and phase separation or drug precipitation.[7]

Droplet size analyzer and polydispersibility index (PDI)

1ml of all formulations was diluted with 100ml of water in a volumetric flask. The volumetric flask was inverted twice to ensure complete dispersion of the formulation. After ensuring complete dispersion of the formulation the droplet size of resultant microemulsion was determined by photon correlation spectroscopy that analyze the fluctuation in light scattering due to the Brownian motion of the droplets as function of time using a zetasizer Nano series. Light scattering was monitored at 25⁰C at 90⁰ angles.[7]

Zeta potential measurements

Zeta potential of formulations was measured by using Malvern Zetasizer equipped with a 4.0mW He-Ne red laser. Zetasizer measures the potential ranged from -30 to 30 v. for measurements of zeta potential 1 ml of each formulations were diluted with 100 ml water.[7]

In vitro dissolution studies

Lurasidone HCl (1ml) SMEDDS formulation was filled in hard gelatin capsule. The *in vitro* release test was performed in 900ml pH 1.2 HCl buffer maintained at 37±0.5⁰c using USP type II dissolution apparatus. The paddles were rotated at 50 rpm. Samples were withdrawn at regular time intervals (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 45, and 60) and replaced with fresh dissolution medium. Samples were filtered using a filter paper. The drug content of the samples was assayed using UV visible spectrophotometric method at 315 nm wavelength and compare to pure drug. All measurements were done in triplicate.[8]

Thermodynamic stability study

1. Heating cooling cycle: six cycles between refrigerator temperatures 4⁰c and room temperature with storage at each temperature of not less than 48 hrs was studied. Suitable formulations at these temperatures were subjected to centrifugation test.

2. Centrifugation: Formulations were passed centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 min then were examined for whether the system is monophasic or biphasic.[8]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solubility of Lurasidone HCl in various excipient

Solubility studies were carried in different surfactant, co-surfactant and oils. The results of these studies are mentioned in figure 1, 2, 3. On the basis of basis of solubility studies, amongst the different surfactant the drug high solubility in Capryol 90, Acrysol K 140, Transcutol P provided higher solubility than other lipid

Figure 1: schematic diagram of drug solubility in different oils.

Figure 2 : Schematic diagram of drug solubility in different –surfactants.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of drug solubility in different co- surfactants.

Drug excipient compatibility study of drug to polymer

Figure 4: Drug excipient compatibility study of drug to polymer.

Table 3: frequency of drug to excipient.

Functional Group	Frequency of Pure Drug (cm ⁻¹)	Frequency of formulation
Ar- H Stretch	2935	2937.88
C=O	1686	1683.56
Ar C=C	1503	1502.60
C-H	1400	1431
C-N	2259	2231

Construction phase diagrams

The construction phase diagrams were constructed by using SIGMA software for the different ratios of surfactant/co-surfactant. The trials were conducted by selecting the points in the pseudo ternary graphs for optimizing the percentage of the surfactant mixture, oil and water in the formulation and the microemulsion formulations were prepared and the optimized formulations were given. The given table 1 and the pseudo ternary plots of F1 to F6 were shown in fig.

Figure .6: Surfactant (Acrysol K 140)/co-surfactant (Transcutol P) ratio 1:1 and oil (Capryol 90).

Figure 7: Surfactant (Acrysol K 140)/co-surfactant (Transcutol P) ratio 2:1 and oil (Capryol 90).

Figure 8: Surfactant (Acrysol K 140)/ co-surfactant (Transcutol P) ratio 1:2 and oil (Capryol 90).

Visual assessments

All formulations are rapid forming microemulsions which are clear or slightly bluish in appearance. Results were shown in Table 4..

Table 4 visual assessment of various formulations.

Formulation code	Grade
F1	I
F2	I
F3	I
F4	I
F5	I
F6	I

% Transmission test of SMEDDS formulations in water The clarity of Microemulsion was checked by transparency, measured in terms of transmittance. SMEDDS forms o/w Microemulsion since water is external phase. Formulation f3 has % transmittance value greater than 99%. These results indicate the high clarity of Microemulsion. In case of other systems % T values were about 98% suggesting less clarity of Microemulsion. Results were shown in Table 5.

Table 5: % Transmittance of f1 to f6 formulations.

Formulation code	% transmission
F1	99.2 ±0.5
F2	99.0±0.1
F3	99.5±0.4
F4	99.3±0.3
F5	98.8±0.1
F6	99.3±0.2

Determination of self emulsification time

The efficiency of self-emulsification could be estimated primarily by determining the rate of emulsification which is an important index for the assessment of the efficiency of emulsion, that is, the SMEDDS should disperse completely and quickly when subjected to aqueous dilution under mild agitation. The emulsification time of these formulations were in the range of 15 to 30 sec. Results were shown in Table 6.

Table 6: selection of oil, surfactant and co-surfactant for SMEDDS formulations.

Formulation code	Emulsification time (sec)
F1	16.44±0.51
F2	23.8±0.43
F3	16.23±0.49
F4	20.5±0.36
F5	26±0.52
F6	30.2±0.17

Drug content

Difference in composition the drug content of formulation f1 to f6 was found in range of 19.7 to 21.7. Results were shown in Table 7.

Table 7: % drug content of F1 to F6 formulations.

Formulation code	% drug content
F1	21.03
F2	19.7
F3	20.33
F4	20.07
F5	21.7
F6	19.15

Particle size analysis

The particle size of microemulsion is important criteria for evaluation and it should be less than 100nm because it determines the rate and extent of drug release as well as absorption. As per his review there is no such specific boundary between SEDDS and SMEDDS. Self emulsification system is similar to SMEDDS, and only difference is in droplet size. An efficient SEDDS should be able to form self emulsion having droplet size less than 5µm. Other formulations which have higher and very lower particle size may get converted to SEDDS upon dilution or during stability period. As depicted in Table 5.18 average particle size was found in water, which range from 19.20-128.4 nm indicating all the particles were in the nanometer range. Results were shown in Table 5.18.

Table 8: Particle size analysis.

Formulation code	Average Particle size in water
F1	22.98
F2	128.4
F3	57.35
F4	105.4
F5	105.9
F6	19.20

Polydispersibility Index (PDI)

Polydispersibility which determines size range of particles in the system is measured by

$$PDI = \frac{\text{No. of particles having size greter than 100nm}}{\text{No. of particles having size less than 100nm}}$$

It is expressed in terms of PDI. An ideal SMEDDS should be widely distributed with particles less than 100nm and so, PDI should be less than 0.3 or in other words particles having size more than 100nm should be maximum up to 23%. The data Table 5.19 shows that formulation F2, F4, F5 have PDI less than 0.3 while in opposite to that f1 and f6 have greater than 0.3. The clarity of Microemulsion was checked by transparency, measured in terms of % Transmission. SMEDDS forms o/w microemulsion since water is in external phase. These results indicate the high clarity of Microemulsion. Results were shown in figure 9, 10, 11, 12,13, 14.

Figure 9: particle size analysis of Batch F1.

Figure 10: particle size analysis of Batch F2.

Figure 11: particle size analysis of Batch F3.

Figure 12: particle size analysis of Batch F4.

Figure 13: particle size analysis of Batch F5.

Figure 14: particle size analysis of Batch F6.

Zeta potential

Zeta potential can be defined as the difference in potential between surface of the tightly bound layer and the electro neutral region of an emulsion. It has got practical application in the stability of emulsion since, zeta potential governs the degree of repulsion between adjacent, similarly charged dispersed droplets. If the zeta potential is reduce below a certain value (which depend on a particular system being used), the attractive forces exceed the repulsion forces, and the particles come together leading to flocculation. The ideal zeta potential for SMEDDS is less than -30mV^5 , all formulations were passing the zeta potential test. Formulation F3 has zeta potential (-13.6) on this basis F3 is optimize. Results were shown in Table 5.20 and figure 5.18, 5.19, 5.20, 5.21, 5.22, 5.23.

Figure 15: zeta potential of Batch F1.

Figure 16: zeta potential of Batch F2.

Figure 17: zeta potential of Batch F3.

Figure 18: zeta potential of Batch F4.

Figure 19: zeta potential of Batch F5.

Figure 20: zeta potential of Batch F6.

In-vitro dissolution studies

In vitro dissolution studies were performed to compare the release of drug from six different SMEDDS formulations (F1-F6) is presented in figure 9. Dissolution studies were performed for the SMEDDS formulations in 0.1 N HCl solutions. There is no any significant difference in dissolution of six SMEDDS formulation. As the emulsification time below 31 s, about 100% of drug released within 50-60 min in case of SMEDDS. The dissolution studies were conducted for 1 hr. to observe the variation or occurrence of precipitation over a time.

Table 9: *In vitro* dissolution studies SMEDDS formulation and pure drug profile F1 to F6.

Time (Min)	% CPR						Pure drug
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	28.68	26.53	32.98	27.60	25.09	26.89	8.96
10	33.35	32.62	41.69	34.44	33.71	34.80	11.57
15	40.93	40.23	49.76	41.34	40.61	41.35	14.47
20	47.93	49.01	57.19	47.96	49.75	47.60	17.11
25	52.80	53.89	66.87	55.72	55.73	53.91	20.03
30	58.44	60.27	74.84	63.57	63.58	61.74	22.70
35	64.15	69.61	84.34	71.50	71.50	67.74	25.66
40	72.07	75.66	93.57	80.23	79.51	73.99	28.72
45	82.25	80.20	99.63	89.42	83.98	80.21	31.35
50	89.64	86.11		99.42	89.20	87.21	34.35
55	95.28	92.08			94.11	93.19	37.82
60	100.25	98.11			100.16	98.50	40.58

Figure 21: *In vitro* dissolution profile and pure drug (Lurasidone HCl).

Thermodynamic stability studies

SMEDDS are thermodynamically stable systems and are formed at a particular concentration of oil, surfactant and water, with no phase separation, creaming or cracking. It is the thermo stability which differentiates nano or microemulsion from emulsion that has kinetic stability and will eventually phase separate. Thus, the selected formulations were subjected to different thermodynamic stability by using heating cooling cycle and centrifugation stress tests.

Table 10: Temperature stability study of f1 to f6 formulation.

FC	4 ⁰ c			Room temperature		
	Phase separation	Flocculation	Precipitation	Phase separation	Flocculation	Precipitation
F1	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen
F2	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen
F3	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen
F4	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen
F5	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen
F6	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen	Not seen

Table 11: Centrifugation stability study of f1 to f6 formulation.

Formulation code	Phase separation
F1	Not seen
F2	Not seen
F3	Not seen
F4	Not seen
F5	Not seen
F6	Not seen

SMEDDS are thermodynamically stable systems and are formed at a particular concentration of oil, surfactant and water, with no phase separation, creaming or cracking. It is the thermo stability which differentiates nano-or Microemulsion from emulsions that have kinetic stability and will eventually phase separate. Thus, the selected formulations were subjected to different thermodynamic stability by using heating cooling cycle and centrifugation tests.

CONCLUSION

Lurasidone HCl is atypical antipsychotic drug which is used in the treatment of schizophrenic patients. It is a highly lipophilic ($\log p$ 5.6), its oral bioavailability which is very low (9-19%) because of its poor solubility. Hence newer approach of self microemulsifying drug delivery system is used to improve the solubility of Lurasidone HCl.

In SMEDDS formulation of Lurasidone HCl were prepared and evaluated for their *in vitro* behavior. Based on solubility studies, capryol 90 (28.40), Acrysol K 140 (79.52) and Transcutol P(24.92) were selected as oil, surfactant and co-surfactant respectively.

An optimized formulation of SMEDDS containing Lurasidone HCl was developed through the construction of ternary phase diagram. As per the phase diagram, stable microemulsion zone was obtained surfactant and co-surfactant in the ratio of 2:1. Formulations were evaluated for visual assessment, self emulsification time, particle size, zeta potential, PDI and *in vitro* dissolution study.

From the evaluation parameter like particle size 57.35nm and PDI 0.288, zeta potential -13.6 mV^5 and *in vitro* 99.63 dissolution study. F3 Formulation was selected as optimized batch formulation, with respect to *in vitro* drug release profile as compared to pure drug (20mg).

REFERENCES

- Goyal U, Gupta A, Rana AC, Aggarwal G. "Self Microemulsifying Drug Delivery System: A method for Enhancement of Bioavailability." Int. J. Pharma. Sci. Res. 2012, 3(1), 66-79.
- Puhan K, Dr. S, Swain SP. "Self Emulsifying Drug Delivery System: an Emergency Paradigm" Int. J. innovative Pharma. Sci. Res. 2014, 2(12), 3050-30-65.
- Structure of lurasidone HCl
<http://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/lurasidone>
- Latuda Drug information 14/8/015
<http://www.dailymed.nlm.nih.gov>
- Stegemanna S, Leveillerb F, "When Poor Solubility becomes an issue: from early stage to proof of concept" European journal of pharmaceutical sciences, 2007, 31.
- Patel PA, Chaulang GM, Hardikar SR, Mutha SS, Akolkotkar A. "Self Emulsifying Drug Delivery System: a review." Res. J. Pharma. Tech. 2008, 1, 313-324.
- Kyatanwar AU, Jadhav KR, Kadam VJ. "Self Micro-emulsifying Drug Delivery System." J. Pharma. Res. 2010, 3, 75-83.
- Shukla P, Prajapati S, Sharma U, Shipra S, Akhtar A. "A review on self micro emulsifying drug delivery system: An approach to enhance the oral bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs." Int. Res. J. Pharma. 2012, 3(9), 1-6.

54878478451160413

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

